

Commercial *Gentefication* as Occupational Activism: How Business Owners Work to Preserve Latinx *Barrios* in Southern California

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The data underlying this article cannot be shared publicly due to the privacy of the individuals who participated.

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ABSTRACT

This article examines how small business owners in gentrifying working-class Mexican-majority *barrios* (neighborhoods) in Southern California engage in occupational activism, using their businesses as platforms to benefit others outside of their workplace. Through interviews and field research, we address the following: What types of occupational activism occur among business owners in Latinx *barrios*? And how do business owners navigate the dilemmas and challenges posed by participating in Latinx-led gentrification as financial activism in the *barrio*? By examining how business owners creatively enact their work roles to promote or resist social change amidst threats of cultural erasure via white-led gentrification, we highlight their workplace dilemma of balancing economic interest, cultural empowerment, and representation. Business owners leverage their workplace roles for community resilience and cultural solidarity, reframing business ownership in the *barrio* as a form of occupational activism rooted in resistance. As occupational activists, business owners incorporate cultural symbols, ethnic pride, and political messaging into their products and services to preserve cultural identity in the *barrio*. Our findings contribute to the growing body of knowledge on occupational activism by highlighting small business owners as key actors in the communities where they work, strengthening cultural ties, and serving as agents of social change in vulnerable communities facing gentrification.

KEYWORDS: Occupational Activism, Latinx business owners, Latinx activism, Gentrification, Urban Politics

INTRODUCTION

The new sociology of work highlights the importance of individual agency and action as a means of social transformation that extends beyond the workplace. The literature on occupational activism thus documents how workers can enact their jobs in ways that contribute to social change (Berg & Kalleberg, 2001; Coley & Schachle, 2023; Cornfield, 2015, 2016, 2023; Hodson, 2001; Pedulla, 2020; Vallas, 2006). However, prior research on occupational activism has primarily focused on workers and their earlier experiences in activism or social movements. In contrast, we focus on the role of small business owners in occupational activism, particularly as they respond to the injustices in the communities where they live and work. The socioeconomic status and access to resources, knowledge, political organizations, networks, and business spaces available to small business owners can empower them to promote activism and amplify the voices of marginalized communities.

Occupational activism is significant for business owners of color who operate in distressed or marginalized neighborhoods. These areas often face ongoing threats of redevelopment or gentrification, leading to various forms of displacement—physical, cultural, and political (Boyd, 2008; Hom, 2023; Hyra, 2015; Pattillo, 2010; Sarmiento, 2022).

Research on working-class Asian and Black neighborhoods undergoing gentrification has examined the role of community elites—specifically, business and property owners with direct economic interests in shaping local development and political decision-making (Knapp & Vojnovic, 2013; Lin, 2008; Pattillo, 2010). However, despite the political and cultural influence of business owners and the potential for social change that comes with ownership, the prevailing understanding in urban sociology has approached the role of business owners as activists with caution. This prior literature tends to emphasize the class-based interests of business owners and

the tensions that arise between them, long-time lower-income residents, and anti-gentrification activists (Ahrens, 2015; Anderson & Sternberg, 2013; Berestein Rojas, 2011; Dávila, 2004; González, 2019; González & Guadiana, 2013; Hom, 2023; Pattillo, 2010).

These dynamics complicate our understanding of racial and ethnic solidarity among community elites in opposition to gentrification due to differences in their social class. Additionally, scholars have noted that business owners of color in gentrifying neighborhoods also often replicate patterns of white-led gentrification (González & Seeley, 2022; Huante, 2021). On the one hand, gentrifiers of color contribute to the commodification of culture and normalize, or even facilitate, the displacement of lower-income residents rather than acting as participants in anti-gentrification efforts through their work (Delgado & Swanson, 2019; Sarmiento, 2022). On the other hand, business owners participate in what Boyd (2008) calls “defensive development” to protect their neighborhoods of color from becoming gentrified by white elites, outside investors, and individuals who do not understand the community.

Upwardly mobile Latinx business owners in predominantly Latinx neighborhoods are increasingly participating in *gentefication*—a term derived from *la gente*, meaning “the people” in Spanish—by highlighting the grassroots and culturally inclusive nature of their work and opposing traditionally white-led gentrification (Berestein Rojas, 2011; Herbst, 2014). In recent years, studies have started to focus on the political activities of Latinx business owners in gentrifying neighborhoods, framing their efforts as forms of activism, community contribution, and a means of political voice and cultural empowerment (Sandoval, 2021; Shmaryahu-Yeshurun, 2024). These business owners, whom we refer to as commercial *gentefiers*, have been critical actors in their retail landscapes, maintaining their culture and commerce while often being overlooked in the literature regarding anti-gentrification mobilization strategies. We argue that rising middle-class

communities of color returning to their working-class neighborhoods to protect them from neoliberal redevelopment threats by “uplifting” them is a form of occupational activism. This perspective—that *gentefication* can serve as occupational activism—has not previously been recognized as such by urban sociologists or the field of new labor activism (Coley & Schachle, 2023; Coley et al., 2022; Cornfield, 2023; Cornfield et al., 2019; Hutchinson et al., 2024). Moreover, the economic and altruistic opportunities presented by *gentefication* prompt us to consider the following questions:

1. What types of occupational activism occur among business owners in Latinx communities facing gentrification?
2. How do Latinx business owners navigate the dilemmas and challenges of participating in Latinx-led gentrification as financial activism?

We draw from interviews and field research conducted with business owners in two Southern California Mexican-majority *barrios*: Barrio Logan in San Diego and Santa Ana in Orange County. Our findings reveal that business owners leverage their occupational platforms by politicizing their products and services through cultural symbols and slogans that emphasize ethnic pride and resistance, fostering a sense of community connection through events and initiatives, and actively engaging in efforts to support and uplift their neighborhoods.

The contribution of our study is twofold. First, we offer a perspective from commercial *gentrifiers* to argue that business ownership in the *barrio* is a form of occupational activism that opposes boycotting businesses in the area as a form of anti-gentrification protest and instead promotes culturally informed economic redevelopment. Commercial *gentefiers* are uniquely sensitive to issues of identity exclusion, racism, and displacement and, therefore, perceive, frame, and operate their businesses as more than economic ventures. Business owners actively strive to

preserve the *barrio* by fostering a sense of cultural pride and identity, and they see their occupational roles extending beyond their storefronts. This perspective contributes to the literature on occupational activism by expanding the focus beyond workers to include small business owners and the spatial context in which this activism occurs. In this way, we also bridge research on the growing Latinx middle class participating in *gentefication* to show how business ownership can serve as a site of occupational activism, offering a community-informed development strategy for ethnic communities threatened by white-led gentrification. Second, we outline the complexities, challenges, and dilemmas business owners face in balancing profit and activism within the broader context of gentrification. We analyze the various ways they navigate these dual demands, contributing to the study of occupational activism. This aspect deepens our understanding of the goals, motivations, and patterns of activism, as well as the inherent challenges, dilemmas, and costs associated with it in their specific community contexts.

BUSINESS OWNERSHIP AS OCCUPATIONAL ACTIVISM IN THE *BARRIO*

Occupational activism, which emerged under the new sociology of work, is “socially transformative, individual, and collective action that is conducted and realized through an occupational role or community” (Cornfield et al., 2019, p. 221). Occupational activism allows workers to utilize their occupational expertise to exercise their voices in and outside their workplace roles as they relate to and contribute to larger-scale social changes (Coley & Schachle, 2023). Therefore, much occupational activism is value-centered as the worker-activist engages in diverse actions on behalf of a group of beneficiaries as a form of political action (Cornfield et al., 2019). Occupational activism is more inherently embedded in some jobs than others (Cornfield et al., 2019). Yet, while not all jobs may explicitly entail social change, workers can still participate in their workplace or society. In their workplace, individuals can leverage the culture of activism

they bring with them, drawing on political experiences from the past to promote values such as the desegregationist principles and nonviolent praxis associated with the civil rights movement (Coley et al., 2022; Cornfield et al., 2019), resist discrimination and hostile work environments for trans and nonbinary workers (Hutchinson et al., 2024) or for students of color (Schachle, & Coley, 2022), as well as promote diversity, equity, and inclusion (Coley & Schachle, 2023).

Understanding the conditions under which occupational activism emerges and flourishes can shed light on its potential outcomes and the types of jobs or industries most conducive to such engagement (Coley & Schachle, 2023). For instance, workplaces that grant employees greater autonomy are more likely to support occupational activism (Cornfield, 2015; Cornfield et al., 2019). Additionally, Cornfield et al. (2019) highlight that occupational activism can also emerge among employees in established occupational settings who have prior experience in social movements. These individuals often carry the ideologies and practices of those movements into their professional roles, shaping how they pursue broader activist goals from within institutionalized contexts. Consequently, much of the research on occupational activism has focused on individuals with a history of movement participation and how their activism manifests in their work (Coley & Schachle, 2023). Expanding this perspective, Augustine and King (2024) argue that social movements not only produce individuals who integrate movement values into their workplaces but also contribute to the creation of entirely new occupations that enable direct engagement with movement-aligned goals—such as affirmative action officers or ethics officers.

Working-class Latinx communities have traditionally been centers of activism focused on housing and workers' rights. The restructuring of the Mexican economy in the 1980s led to a significant influx of workers who established *barrios* in the United States (Hernández-León, 2004). These *barrios* have been marked by discriminatory policies, uneven development, inflated

rents, and low-wage jobs, resulting in high unemployment, disinvestment, and poverty. In response to challenges faced by *barrio* residents, activism and resistance flourished, making *barrios* crucial locations for cultural solidarity, self-determination, political mobilization, and civil rights efforts. Working-class *barrios* have thus demonstrated resilience in the face of structural inequality through ethnic solidarity and collective action, becoming spaces that promote cultural preservation for resistance and survival.

The cohesion, ethnic solidarity, cultural heritage, and economic well-being of *barrios* continue to be threatened today by the pressures of gentrification. *Barrio* residents have mobilized by organizing protests and boycotts of city policies, businesses, and events when faced with commercial gentrification, a change in the class status of firms in an area's retail sector (González 2017; González et al. 2012). This process, whereby culture creates an opportunity for economic profit and preservation, suggests business owners want to remain connected to their ethnic communities despite their class-based mobility and fear of *barrios*' cultural displacement (Ahrens 2015; Anderson & Sternberg 2013; Berestein Rojas 2011; Delgado & Swanson 2021; Herbst 2014; Shmaryahu- Yeshurun, 2024).

Small business owners, especially those in Latinx *barrios*, are autonomous workers actively engaging in activism and driving social change. An extensive body of literature has documented how *barrios* have provided economic opportunity to immigrant business owners serving a niche market, providing services in their native language and products reminiscent of their country of origin, and meeting both the cultural and economic needs of residents (Gold & Light 2000; Logan et al., 2002; Portes, 1995; Waldinger, 1989; Zhou 2004). While owning a business in the *barrio* was previously studied as a temporary and exclusive occupation for immigrant populations, it is now a platform for subsequent generations' future employment inside

and outside of the *barrio* (Aldrich & Waldinger, 1990; Valdez, 2008) with the resurgence of upwardly mobile U.S.-born individuals opening businesses after obtaining forms of capital (e.g., a college education) and participating in Latinx-led gentrification (Ahrens, 2015; Aguis Vallejo, 2012; Aguis Vallejo & Canizales, 2016; Dávila, 2004; Delgado & Swanson, 2021; González 2019; Huante 2021). New businesses, due to commercial *gentefication* in the *barrio*, signal who the retail sector is intended to serve in part due to the actions of its workers who curate the space: small business owners. For example, inherent in some *gentefied* areas is the commodification of Latinx culture for profit by selling ethnic products and cultural materials to in- and out-group members to contribute to the cultural production of place (Anderson & Sternberg, 2013; Dávila, 2004). As a result, business owners who participate in commercial *gentefication* stay in the *barrio* for reasons outside of economic opportunity alone.

The Latinx middle and upper classes, defined by educational attainment that correlates with income, occupation, and wealth attainment (Kochhar & Sechopoulos, 2022), are a diverse and complex group shaped by racialization, heterogeneity in class origin, class-heterogeneous kin ties, and legal status vulnerabilities, all of which interact to shape pathways and experiences (Aguis Vallejo & Vasquez-Tokos, 2024). The diverse contexts of the Latinx middle class provide an opportunity to examine the heterogeneity of occupational mobility pathways such as business ownership (Aguis Vallejo & Canizales, 2023). According to Aguis Vallejo and Vasquez-Tokos' (2024) analysis of American Community Survey (ACS) data, 44% of Latinx households are in the middle-income category, compared with 43.5% of Black households, 47% of Asian American households, and 52% of White households (Ruggles et al., 2024). Latinx business owners with growing wealth have created economic institutions to transmit social and economic capital through financial activism (Aguis Vallejo & Canizales, 2016). In their study of Latinx middle-class and

elites, Aguis Vallejo and Canizales (2023) find that racialized groups leverage their ethnicity for financial activism to their coethnic community. By offering professional services from their advanced training as an influential means of “giving back,” Latinx middle-class and elites’ roles inside and outside of their businesses have yet to be acknowledged by research on occupational activism (Aguis Vallejo, 2012; Aguis Vallejo & Canizales, 2016). Latinx business owners in *gentefying* areas have demonstrated that they leverage their economic status, networks, and ethnic solidarity to engage in urban politics and planning, amplifying their community’s political voice and cultural empowerment (Shmaryahu-Yeshurun, 2024).

These recent studies reinforce earlier literature on business owners and gentrifiers from racial and ethnic groups—primarily Black and Asian—and highlight their solidarity with their ethnic communities and their efforts to strengthen the cultural character of the space. Studying Black gentrifiers in North Kenwood–Oakland in Chicago, Pattillo (2010) describes them as “middlemen”—mediators between community needs and policymakers, working to improve and support the community. Similarly, Boyd (2008) described Black elites engaging in “defensive development” (p. 752), focusing on community building and economic revitalization to protect neighborhoods from white gentrifiers, city elites, and developers. Furthermore, Black gentrifiers in Brickton, Philadelphia, were described as preventing displacement, buffering against white gentrification, and promoting racial uplift and affordable housing (Moore, 2009).

We contribute to this research by showing how business owners combine multiple work roles, balancing economic and noneconomic reasons—or “dilemma work,” as described by Chong (2021)—where they must choose between the extent to which they participate in or condone *gentefication* as being in conflict or aligned with their identity and values. This form of “dilemma work”—commercial *gentefiers*’ competing demands of the *barrio* and business ventures—

contributes to the literature on occupational activism (Coley & Schachle, 2023; Coley et al., 2022; Cornfield, 2023; Cornfield et al., 2019; Hutchinson et al., 2024), where workers who belong to marginalized groups serve as critical political actors to promote values in their workplaces and resist hostile or discriminatory environments in the larger context of gentrification.

DATA AND METHODS

Data are drawn from the authors' larger qualitative projects in two Southern California Mexican-majority *barrios*: Barrio Logan in San Diego and Santa Ana in Orange County (see Table 1 for neighborhood characteristics). Barrio Logan has a population of about 4,000 residents, and the percentage of Latinx residents dropped from 83 percent in 2000 to 71 percent in 2019. In the same period, the white population grew from six percent in 2000 to 20 percent in 2019 (U.S. Census Bureau, 2000, 2020). Eighty-five percent of the 60 businesses established in the last decade on Logan Avenue and 26th are owned by Latinxs¹. Santa Ana, CA, is a majority-Mexican city in the heart of a predominately white and middle-class Orange County. Santa Ana is home to a population of 330,000 people with a 77% Latinx demographic (a majority being Mexican-origin), and as of 2018, 44.6% of Santa Ana residents were born outside of the United States. The business sector of Santa Ana is represented by 68% minority owned businesses, specifically 48% Latinx-owned (U.S. Census Bureau, 2015).

[Table 1 here]

We use a qualitative in-depth case study approach to draw from interviews and fieldwork (Yin, 2003). First, we conducted semi-structured interviews with 40 business owners in Barrio Logan and 43 in Santa Ana, including owners of restaurants, stores, art galleries, coffee shops, and

¹The information is based on street tour and mapping Author Two conducted, analysis of information from the Google Maps engine, interviews with business owners, and information from the City of San Diego.

bars (see Table 2 for demographics of the participants). We recruited business owners using both snowball and purposeful sampling by attending community meetings of various organizations and building rapport. We aimed to include a diverse range of business owners in terms of gender, time in the neighborhood, and business type. However, by its nature, commercial gentrification tends to attract a certain type of business—what Zukin (2015) terms the “ABC” of gentrification: art galleries, boutiques, and cafés. As a result, these types of businesses make up a relatively high proportion of our sample. In terms of business tenure, on the main commercial street of Logan Avenue in Barrio Logan, most businesses are relatively young and newly established, which is why they make up most of our sample. In Santa Ana, however, we also included some longer-standing businesses in the sample. For a detailed categorization of business types, see our previous publication (Shmaryahu-Yeshurun & Muñiz, 2025) as well as Table 2. Interviews were an average of 60 minutes, conducted in-person in English, Spanish, and *Spanglish*, audiotaped and transcribed verbatim. Participants’ identities are anonymized for confidentiality following Institutional Review Board protocols.

[Table 2 here]

Second, we conducted participant observations at events, meetings, and organizations in charge of planning and programming in both neighborhoods. In Barrio Logan, data were collected at monthly meetings of local organizations that included the following organizations: All For Logan, the Barrio Logan Association, the Chicano Park Steering Committee, and a community planning group. In Santa Ana, we attended city council meetings, board meetings, and events for the two business organizations under Santa Ana’s business improvement district (BID) that collected funds from business license fees and oversaw re-distributing funds through programming efforts. Both authors also observed the cultural, political, and arts events in the two respective

neighborhoods, including Chicano Park Day celebrations, national and cultural holidays such as *Fiestas Patrias* for Mexican Independence Day, *Dia de los Muertos* or Day of the Dead, “Walk the Block” initiative events, “Art Walks,” political events and rallies, and social activities. Both authors also participated in events initiated by their respondents such as festivals, shows, art exhibitions, and workshops.

We used thematic analysis for identifying, analyzing, and reporting themes within our data (Clarke & Braun, 2016). Our analysis was deductive and inductive, guided by our initial theoretical frameworks, and based on the patterns that arose from the data (Tavory & Timmermans, 2014). Data were coded into themes using qualitative analysis software NVivo and Dedoose about the mobilization of ethnic communities facing *gentefication* in the areas of local politics, finances, business operations, and business owners’ family and personal histories. The authors wrote memos throughout the data analysis process and met to discuss patterns in our data as well as histories of the two communities.

We center the narratives of our participants—business owners in our two field sites—as situated accounts that reflect how they make sense of their work and community roles, constraints, and agency. While we do not claim business owners’ narratives are free from economic self-interest, we prioritize them as critical contributions that we triangulated based on our multifaceted approach at data collection that allowed us to have a prolonged and sustained engagement at our field sites accounting for what business owners say (e.g., our interview data) and what they do (e.g., our ethnographic fieldwork).

COMMERCIAL *GENTEFICATION* AS BUSINESS OWNERS’ ACTIVIST WORK

In the following sections we show how business ownership in the *barrio* is a form of occupational financial activism by providing two examples of dilemmas they navigate in their workplace roles

as participants in *gentefication*. Commercial *gentefiers*' altruistic culturally informed work provides them with the agency to express their financial and activist roles in the *barrio*. As a result, these business owners must (1) mediate the dilemma of balancing the line between cultural representation and commercialization and (2) navigate providing consumers with affordable products while maximizing their profits. These two dilemmas we present below further demonstrate the ongoing tension business owners face between using their workplace as a space for empowerment, cultural representation, and political voice on the one hand and advancing their economic interest on the other hand.

Business Ownership in the Barrio as Altruistic Financial Activism

Commercial *gentefiers* described being attuned to issues of identity exclusion, racism, and displacement, and therefore see and frame their businesses as more than economic ventures. Commercial *gentefiers* expressed a strong sense of belonging and a desire to contribute to the *barrio* through their businesses. Owning a business in the *barrio* became commercial *gentefiers*' alternative to activist approaches that boycott or withdraw patronage from its retail sector, instead symbolizing a financial and cultural reinvestment due to their economic capital. To open and own a business in both Barrio Logan and Santa Ana became a political act, a form of resistance and a stand against external forces driving gentrification in the area, and an avenue for giving back to the community as both economic and cultural stakeholders. Establishing and owning businesses in the *barrio* while it is being threatened by gentrification means asserting presence and claiming space ownership.

In Santa Ana, business owners frame financial activism as a separate and sometimes opposing form of activism, distinct to that of long-term residents and local activists, whose approach often includes boycotting business activity. Anti-gentrification activists in Santa Ana

have largely withdrawn their support from all downtown businesses (including Latinx owned businesses) for their implied affiliation with and support of gentrification, *gentefication*, and/or allegiance with city representatives. This divergence often created tension between residents/activists and business owners over the appropriate way to lead change and promote the community. Local activists who opposed Santa Ana businesses failed to recognize the forms of activism that business owners were also engaging in to maintain and sustain the commercial corridor and its Latinx identity. Miriam is a forty-four-year-old consultant for downtown Santa Ana businesses who, despite her prior movement experience, expresses disagreement with anti-gentrification activists' approach to withdrawing their support from its businesses. Miriam says that, although she used to work alongside activists and nonprofits "fighting in city hall," she now believes the most vocal anti-gentrification activists are "largely misguided." Instead, Miriam now works with new and longtime business owners to problem solve, grant write and bring money into their business organizations to redistribute into the *barrio* via events and programming; these business owners, she claims, are "demonized for being capitalist" rather than understood as also being anti-gentrification activists. Miriam explains that the work of the business owners she collaborates with is important because,

To me, boycotting means that you're withdrawing your resources from your own community so that you're actually quickening the pace of what you're saying that you want to actually protect it from. So, my strategy, and also other people that I talk to is, 'No. We have to do the opposite. You have to actually not boycott. You need to get everybody to come down from their own community to maintain the marketplace that says that it's for them, and having the marketplace have to modify to the clientele base.'

Boycotting downtown Santa Ana businesses, according to Miriam, only worsens the marginalization of community-minded business owners and quickens white-led gentrification that activists are trying to stop. To Miriam, both consumers and producers (e.g., business owners) must adapt and modify their approaches (e.g., participate in its *gentefication*) to suit the current state of

its commercial sector. The adaptability of the *barrio* is essential to preserve its culture and prevent it from being developed further away from its roots.

Similar to Miriam, Sarahi sees being a business owner in Santa Ana as a way to have stakes in the future of the *barrio*. Sarahi, a mid-forties writer, poet, and owner of an art gallery and bookstore in Santa Ana, emphasizes she had two main goals in establishing her business: economic profit and community benefit in the landscape of *barrios* being threatened with cultural erasure.

Sarahi says,

Yes, we're always gonna change, but how do we maintain and hold space and, and continue to have visibility in our community? I learned through the years that it's not through protesting and boycotting, I mean you boycott, that's where you're giving them what they want. And so, and then the only way to have any type of equity is to have money. And so that's why I started to build a business.

Sarahi explains that she is doing the opposite of boycotting and working within current structures on her own terms by owning a business that embraces Mexican ethnic identity. The counter to not being involved becomes what Sarahi describes as a pattern happening in areas like downtown Santa Ana across the United States: “people of color are disappearing from downtowns across the nation—and we can't disappear. This country has a long history of making people disappear.” Cultural erasure because of community change, whether talked about as gentrification or not in areas like Santa Ana and across the United States, demonstrates why individuals like Sarahi choose to persist.

Furthermore, the growing demand for cultural consumption—celebrating Mexican culture, food, music, vibrant art, and murals—is transforming Latinx neighborhoods into desirable sites of “ethnic consumption” (Anderson & Sternberg 2013). This intersection between cultural demand and activism reflects a blend of economic profit and altruism, motivating occupational activism and reinforcing the belief that practices like cultural consumption, rather than boycotts, can serve

as effective forms of activism. Consequently, the establishment of Latinx-owned businesses is viewed as an act of occupational activism that represents a claim to space ownership in the *barrio* that celebrates Latinx culture and fosters social change. Andrea is a commercial *gentefier* in Santa Ana with a restaurant; she notes how the work she is doing in the *barrio* is more than serving people good food:

All the restaurants that I worked for were great, I learned a lot of things from them. But this one I felt like they were changing the world in a way. I felt like they were changing people's perceptions, perceptions of Mexican food and by default changing people's perceptions of Mexicans. And I felt like that was really really important. And so I think that was the first time that I really like thought like restaurant can be like a really helpful thing like a restaurant and like inspire social change. Like a restaurant can be a vehicle to like make people think differently.

In Barrio Logan, business owners echoed sentiments similar to Sarahi in Santa Ana, who described the gentrification of communities of color nationwide and the pressure on business owners to adjust to shifting demographics, rising costs, and changing neighborhood identities. Juan, who owns an ice cream shop and gallery in Barrio Logan, explains that opening a business is very intentional; it is an act of political influence on urban policy, an activist effort more effective than protests and rallies since it occurs every day through his work:

Gentrification is here, what do you choose to do with it? Is it important to go out there and raise your fist and protest? What is it that you're protesting? Gentrification happens to every town in America. You can't stop progress, but you can steer it in the proper direction...We can be the victims forever or we can advocate and find out how to be part of it.. You got to work with the system, you can protest in a different way, legal fashion, sit on a table and talk about it. Now we have businesses, organizations...It's gone through a metamorphosis; we are providing business economic development to better the community.

Juan suggests that gentrification is so widespread that, once it has arrived, the solution is not to protest. Juan explains that “progress” as exemplified by changes in the city cannot be stopped as a result of external pressures that bring on redevelopment; rather, people should invest themselves

in the process, and there is power in that. Commercial *gentefiers* in both Barrio Logan and Santa Ana echo Juan's perspective that owning a business is a way to protest. By forming business organizations and groups, advocacy grows in the *barrio* alongside economic redevelopment—an ongoing process business owners feel powerless to stop, leading to their dilemma over whether to join and shape gentrification, or resist it.

Latinx business owners emphasize the importance of financial activism as a metamorphosis of community activism—one that aims to promote social change by participating in the “rules of the game.” However, unlike the business owners in Santa Ana, they tend to frame their financial activism as complementary to, rather than in opposition to, local activism. This is reflected in the fact that some business owners also participate in protests and boycotts against new non-Latinx businesses and corporations entering the neighborhood and maintain close collaborations with community activists, including the Chicano Park Steering Committee. This can be explained, in part, by the fact that some of them grew up in Barrio Logan in families that were involved in the historic struggle for Chicano Park, which remains a powerful source of inspiration and activism in Barrio Logan today. This blending of activism forms can also be understood as aligned with their economic interests, as Chicano Park and the activism surrounding it are located at the heart of the commercial corridor in which they operate, attracting tourism and cultural consumers.

The story of activism surrounding Chicano Park in Barrio Logan unfolded in the 1970s, alongside the rise of the Chicano movement. Following the construction of the San Diego-Coronado Bridge in 1969—which displaced families and divided the community to connect downtown San Diego to the affluent neighborhood of Coronado—the city further exacerbated tensions by deciding to build a California Highway Patrol substation beneath the bridge. In response, residents and activists resisted and instead constructed what is now known as Chicano

Park. Home to over 100 murals, and designated a National Historic Landmark in 2016, the park stands as a powerful symbol of resistance against spatial injustice and serves as a hub for Latinx rights advocacy.

Sofia, a 48-year-old clothing store owner born and raised in Barrio Logan, explains that owning a business has become a way for her to also give back to her community: “for me, to come back on a positive note, like as an entrepreneur, as a woman educated or already with a college degree, a different view of life was important to me...I was very involved years back with a lot of community events...I come from a very political family, that was a big advocate of this community and the Chicano movement, which worked alongside with Cesar Chavez.” In both communities, many respondents grew up in the area and, after earning their college degrees, returned to the *barrio* to reinvest by starting their businesses. By moving back to the *barrio*, these business owners aimed to show potential customers that they were positive influences—a role they had aspired to during their youth when they felt they had few role models. Sofia further explains how, despite feeling lost as a youth, doing what she calls “wrong things” when she went to college, she “came... back as an advocate” and “now I’m back doing this [owning a clothing store].” She explains that her goal is to work with you: “tell me what you need, and I can kind of guide you.” Establishing and owning a business has become a form of community-rooted and financial activism, where returning commercial *gentefiers* like Sofia transform past struggles into a platform for guidance and empowerment, seeking to show that success can grow from the very roots that once held the community back.

Dilemma 1: Balancing Representation and Commercialization

Despite business owners’ clear statements regarding the intertwining of their political and economic goals through their work, they face underlying contradictions, dilemmas, and challenges

balancing between the two. The first challenge is how business owners use culture not just to attract customers, but as a way to assert cultural and political identity—positioning Latinx identity as a form of empowerment rather than simply a commodity for profit. As a result, commercial *gentefiers* empower and preserve Latinx culture while amplifying the voice of their community through the products and services offered in their businesses. This form of occupational activism is exemplified through the sale of culturally significant products and the creation of art and murals aimed at reinforcing the representation and voice of the local Latinx community. This work is especially challenging in light of criticism from local activists who claim that commercial *gentefiers* are only motivated by profit and exploit the community and its culture for economic gain.

In the *barrios* of our study, galleries, exhibitions, art events, murals, and street graffiti play a significant role in promoting Latinx empowerment and local voices, as opposed to the cultural erasure brought on by art galleries and creative classes in traditionally gentrifying areas. First, Latinx-owned art galleries employ local residents and showcase the works of local and Latinx artists, giving them an opportunity to gain recognition during the early stages of their careers. Additionally, many galleries offer free or nominal-fee workspaces for artists. Secondly, these galleries contribute to the accessibility of art and culture for economically disadvantaged communities and residents. By making art more available, they bridge gaps in cultural participation and ensure that individuals from all backgrounds can engage with artistic expressions. Thirdly, the development of local Latinx art and the beautification of neighborhoods outwardly depict a positive representation of ethnic backgrounds and histories, countering the prevailing stereotypes of these areas as centers of crime, poverty, and neglect. Moreover, the art displayed in these galleries not only celebrates Latinx culture but also conveys powerful messages related to local

and broader political discourse. Topics such as gentrification, whitewashing, United States war policies, immigration policies, capitalism, and racism are often addressed through the artwork, sparking conversations and raising awareness. Finally, some galleries serve as spaces for community and political organization. They host art exhibitions, poetry slam evenings, and a variety of community and political events, fostering a sense of belonging, unity, and activism within the Latinx community.

The cultural activism of art galleries of commercial *gentefiers* also poses challenges against the criticism and concern over the exploitation and commodification of culture for profit. Edgar, for example, is a 52-year-old Mexican American artist and owner of an art gallery that was established in Santa Ana in 2003. Through art, Edgar reinvents Mexican American culture. Edgar acknowledges the field he is in is classist and heavily based in predominantly white upper-middle-class areas of Orange County as opposed to Santa Ana. When displaying his work in community forums, Edgar explains he is reminded of why he does his work:

I've had every walk of life come up and thank me for being here, for no other reason that my skin was the same color as their skin. And in that I saw that this is where I can make a difference. This is where I could, just, by being here, I can make a difference and, and have those kids that are walking into my gallery now, I can't tell you how many times I'll have a little kid who doesn't say anything, but he's looking at the color of my skin or he's looking at, you know, the color of my hair and saying, 'I could do this.'

Edgar wants Mexican Americans to be awakened because he feels that he comes from a lot of privilege. Through his role as a business owner, he wants to “teach future generations what it's like to be spontaneous, self-sustaining, imaginative, and culturally aware.” The work that artists are doing to inspire others through their ideologies around their work and community engagement is altruistic. As part of Latinx artists’ desire to inspire and encourage local artists, business owners and artists organized and built the Santa Ana Arts and Culture Master Plan and Artists’ Registry.

Randall, a consultant for a downtown Santa Ana business organization, explains how they are boosting the arts, as it is crucial to the area:

We make maps and guides and write articles about downtown, so people know what's going on down here. I guess we also emphasize that we support artists. We built the Santa Ana artists' registry so that artists could get jobs and sustain themselves in the community, because we have the Arts District. We see downtown as a really creative place, both in traditional arts but also media arts and startups and things like that.

This project aims to do more than just provide information and accessibility to local artists; it aspires to ignite a sense of pride and empowerment in the realm of art and local Latinx artists.

A recurring theme that emerged in interviews was the perceived exclusion of Latinx artists. This exclusion was seen as originating from both the city and society at large, as well as from within the Latinx community itself. Sarahi, bookstore owner and writer in Santa Ana, sheds light on this perspective:

A lot of times when people are looking for entertainment, whether it's arts, they look for outside, they never look inside. Why? Because people value people from other places more than they value those at their doorstep. ... There's murals here that people got brought in from Europe to paint, when we have folks fighting for walls here to paint, right? and again and it also goes back to classes... classification where just 'cause it's European means it's automatically higher art, right? Versus whether it's Mexican or street art. Um, and so I think a lot of it has to do is, we have to create a presence, a whole space, so that people recognize that there is, we are evolving, that we are part of this art scene, that we are part of these businesses which is not in the main stream canon way. we are thinking differently and there's nothing wrong with that, it's not a lesser class, it's just different. And we are part of this American society, where we having are these thoughts based on what we see in our home, based on what we see when we leave our homes, and based on what we see are community needs.

Sarahi brings up how Latinx culture has not been prioritized or represented as entertainment or artistic in the canon and has been largely overshadowed. She explains that instead of looking inward to celebrate and acknowledge Latinx culture, Latinx communities are losing out on their economic and cultural value. Thus, commercial *gentefiers* work to empower artisans, and supporting local art is more than just a means of sustaining the local community amid gentrification

and exclusion; it is also seen as an opportunity to challenge what is considered “mainstream” art. Murals on Santa Ana storefronts were once primarily political, depicting the struggles and contributions of working-class neighborhoods in local labor movements. Today, while they continue to reference Mexican culture and Santa Ana’s history, these murals have also been repurposed as visual branding—used to attract visitors and market the area as culturally vibrant.

In Barrio Logan, the historic struggle for Chicano Park, which involved protesting through murals, forms the basis and inspiration for activism through art. Chicano Park is the hub of an emerging arts district, boasting galleries, numerous artist collectives, and art events, including the monthly Barrio Art Crawl. Barrio Art Crawl events were initiated by the Logan Avenue Consortium (LAC). Later, the organization was closed and replaced by All for Logan (AFL), a community origination that unifies the Logan Avenue business district. The group is dedicated to promoting arts, cultural events, and local businesses on Historic Logan Avenue. The Barrio Art Crawl invites the public to tour the murals, open studios, galleries, food vendors, live street music, and local businesses throughout Barrio Logan.

As of 2023, there are 24 art galleries in Barrio Logan. The first gallery that was established on Logan Avenue, near Chicano Park, was La Bodega Gallery in 2014; it was founded by Sonia Lopez Chavez, a self-taught artist from Guanajuato, Mexico, and the local artist Chris Zertuche. The owners’ aim was to create an art hub for Barrio Logan’s local artists and community and to offer the community direct access to various forms of art. This was achieved through exhibitions, performance events, and screenings; the gallery also hosted over 100 shows that include the popular annual “Dia De Los Muertos Skull Art Show,” “Frida Kahlo Art Show,” “Perfect 10,” and many more. The establishment of the gallery itself promoted the beautification of the neighborhood, as it was situated in an abandoned junkyard within an empty block. After renting

the space, Sonia and Chris undertook various renovations and constructed studios available for artists to rent at an affordable price. They also adorned the exterior walls facing the street with iconic murals that celebrate Mexican identity and culture, such as the mural featuring Frida Kahlo. Unfortunately, in 2019, Sonia and Chris were forced to close their gallery after being informed of a substantial rent increase (four times higher than before). This event sparked a campaign and united activists, artists, and business owners in a fight against gentrification, bringing the issue to the forefront. While La Bodega Gallery eventually closed its doors, its story served as a catalyst, inspiring other business owners to establish art galleries in the neighborhood. This resulted in the subsequent flourishing of additional galleries on the same block. Moreover, it prompted businesses and galleries to engage in political discourse, realizing the need for collective organization and action against gentrification.

A notable example of a gallery that emerged around the same time as the closure of La Bodega is an art gallery called Aztlán, known for its political messages and community organization. The gallery was established with the aim of sustaining the Latinx community and claiming indigenous ownership of the space they called Aztlán, an area of debated historical accuracy. The Chicano community reveres Aztlán as the ancestral home of the Aztec peoples before the United States occupied it in 1848. The owners of the gallery, a couple named Valeria and Diego, are active members in the community. Valeria is also a muralist in Chicano Park, while Diego grew up in an activist family that fought for Chicano Park and is himself the chairman of the Chicano Park Steering Committee. Since the Gallery establishment, they have hosted exhibitions and art shows focusing on the historical struggle over Chicano Park, gentrification, Chicano identity, and their experiences as first generation immigrants.

Latinx-owned galleries also provide space for an association of political activists and lecturers, events and workshops on various topics such as the Chicano Movement, community organizations, and grassroots campaigns. Activism through art galleries seeks to promote initiative and implement a policy alternative instead of waiting for a policy to adapt itself to the community. As Diego in Barrio Logan explained,

This gallery is more like a community space, to sustain the community...to help our brothers and sisters who are getting displaced... We make sure we are not being priced out of our land...We view these businesses as getting that type of political power, a strong sense of Chicano identity... knowing that we can fight and push these policymakers but also do for ourselves...Because at the end of the day, we know these political institutions weren't built for us...instead of always pushing the government to do this for us; some of the things, like creating business support, community welfare, can be community-led, and it's okay to have your own political power.

The art scene in Latinx barrios plays a crucial role in promoting empowerment and cultural enrichment. Latinx-owned art galleries employ residents, provide platforms for local artists, and offer affordable workspaces. These galleries also enhance accessibility to art and culture for economically disadvantaged communities, challenging cultural participation gaps. Additionally, the development of local Latinx art and the presence of murals in neighborhoods challenge negative stereotypes and convey political messages. Art galleries often serve as spaces for community engagement, hosting events and fostering a sense of belonging and activism. Despite challenges, artists and commercial *gentefiers* strive to create alternative spaces and empower local communities through art.

Latinx-owned galleries also face criticism from local activists about whether the culture they present properly reflects the community and its political message or merely serves as cultural commodification. Diego, for example, explained that he made the decision not to sell “just anything”; the items he sells are carefully screened. His criterion is to avoid selling artworks that are popular or visually appealing solely because they are icons like portraits of Frida Kahlo or

works that romanticize Latin culture. Instead, he chooses pieces with bold, even controversial messages that align with his political vision. As an example, Diego shared that he continued selling a piece by a local artist, even though it made some people uncomfortable and even deterred some customers due to its political message opposing racism and gentrification. The artwork depicts a Native figure chained by a white man and woman, representing hipsters or gentrifiers. Diego explained:

I am not afraid to say the real history and tell people that this is a Chicano community, and if you want to support me take a back seat... we meet with tour groups too, they'll come here, talk, and ask questions. But we're going to tell you the real deal, we're going to tell you about the history of the racism in this community, that we're Chicano, about Chicago nationalist space. You don't have to come and we're not going to hand you the wheel, you're going to come and learn from what we're doing. And if someone really wants to support our community, they won't feel offended, they won't feel like, oh, you're, not letting me feel welcome. We have a sign right in front, saying "racist and cops are not welcome here". And we stand by that, for us, it's not being afraid to tell outsiders that versus trying to cater to them.... You do get outreach and you can get people to come support initiatives, but it's making sure you're not selling out while doing that.

In several art galleries in Barrio Logan, you can find artworks with significant cultural and political messages, like Diego mentioned, including signs and artworks that say "Abolish ICE," "Fuck the police²," "Daughter of an immigrant," "We want to have fundamental human rights," and "First generation but not the last." Another artist in Barrio Logan explained his "method" for balancing financial gain with a political voice: "I do what I feel good about... I won't do something I'll regret just because it makes me money." He shared that, over the years, he has turned down customer requests for artworks that he felt commodified the culture and lacked authenticity.

Dilemma 2: Navigating Affordable Products and Profit Maximization

Commercial *gentefiers'* second dilemma involves whether to prioritize profit by catering to wealthier clientele or to keep prices affordable for local working-class residents, even at a financial

² ICE: Immigration and Customs Enforcement

cost. This dynamic compels them to balance their desire to provide a political voice and support community empowerment with the practical demands of sustaining a profitable business. These tensions shape the way they approach their business strategies and engagement with the community. In the reality of rising rents amidst redevelopment projects, commercial *gentefiers* face competing demands about their businesses. On the one hand, they must cater to the local working-class community by offering affordable services and products. On the other hand, they must attract customers from outside the neighborhood—tourists and consumers—who are willing to pay higher prices for goods that are often beyond the reach of the local community. Some commercial *gentefiers* aim to reflect the values, traditions, and artistry of the community and remain "loyal" to the local clientele, making an effort to offer products that meet the demand of this target audience and at an affordable price. In doing so, they view their day-to-day work activities in their businesses as inherently political acts. Omar, a business owner in Santa Ana, recognizes that his business' presence and efforts to prioritize the local community serve as a form of political expression:

Look, me existing is a political statement. For me this place [his business] means a lot, it's a political statement, it's a point of pride, it's as I said, unforgivably Mexican. I try to also identify not only with back in Mexico, in the homeland, but also what is to be the Mexican American experience in the States. You know, like the Tigres del Norte say, '*ni de aqui ni de alla.*'

Omar explains that other businesses, which are more established, have done so well because their Mexican-American identity has flown under the radar, making them palatable to additional audiences. These other businesses have broadened out to a larger Latinx category that is more accessible by catering to whiteness. Omar is wary of businesses that use Mexican ethnic identity as a marketing tactic, attempting to "walk a fine line" by attracting both Latinx and outside customers rather than operating with a genuine political purpose, he explains:

I've seen a lot of businesses, some businesses that you know, have something tagged as in you know, 'we're Latino, we're Mexican.' They started trying to pander a little bit more to Latinos. 'Hispander' as they say sometimes.

Stephanie, in her early 40s, grew up in a working-class neighborhood similar to Santa Ana. Initially unfamiliar with the city, she was aware of its negative perception due to its high rates of poverty, homeless population, and multiple failed attempts at gentrification. Transitioning from a career as a paralegal, she stumbled into owning a bar. Stephanie's introduction to Santa Ana came through its thriving bar scene and LGBT nightlife. A friend offered her the opportunity to own a bar, which was previously a gathering place for working-class Mexican immigrants. Stephanie, a second-generation South American, identifies with the Mexican American experience and talks about how the space used to be a "paisa bar" meaning it did not sell craft beer but was a place for working-class Mexican immigrants. The bar Stephanie owns she explains has not departed much from its origin,

I think we try to cater to the culture of Santa Ana and not change it. We're not trying to gentrify it. You know like per se so many other places or people who were, you know in the beginning, that was a big struggle. People are thinking we are trying to gentrify. but we're not. We try to keep the culture. We have *rock en español* nights and our Chicano DJ night. But yeah, I think we keep that culture alive here.

Being culturally aware, informed, and thoughtful was a pattern demonstrated by business owners in both barrios. Stephanie explains that although her business used to be more "*paisa*," meaning the customer base was homogenous working-class, she worked to demonstrate that her business had the same goals of maintaining Santa Ana's Mexican ethnic identity through its new craft beer identity. Given generational shifts in the community, newer businesses owned by respondents present themselves differently than prior establishments. At the same time, and despite the fact that some businesses do indeed cater to an outside audience, many business owners remain aware of the needs of the local community. They offer some products at affordable prices, donate items

such as clothing or food to vulnerable community members, and provide services and workshops at discounted rates for locals. In most cases, *gentefiers* employ a mix of strategies, catering to both traditional and new clientele with the understanding that they are not maximizing their profits.

Similar patterns have been observed in Barrio Logan, where a business association called “All for Logan” organizes annual events and workshops, often offering discounted or free tickets for the local community. However, the need to make a living and survive economically amid gentrification leads many businesses to target an external audience, offering products at prices that are often beyond the reach of residents. For example, at a clothing studio, you can find jackets priced between \$110 and \$180, and although exceptional, a vintage handmade jacket was offered at an impressive price of \$525. In a nearby gallery, paintings were priced in the hundreds. Camila, the owner of the studio, is a Latina who grew up in California and moved to Barrio Logan to open her studio. Her studio attracts a diverse clientele, including young people, hipsters, tourists, and many gentrifiers. In the clothing she sews, all handcrafted and made from recycled materials, she incorporates phrases like “Brown AF,” “Brown Queen,” “Morena,” “Chicana,” and “Bonita” to convey a political message that challenges the American beauty standards and strengthens Chicano identity. She explains the sometimes-high prices by emphasizing the quality of her work:

This is a business, and I need to make a living. I also have rent to pay. There are many things here at very good prices, but there are also more expensive items that reflect my work. As a second-generation immigrant who has worked hard my whole life, we deserve to make a living too, and I hope the community supports that.

She adds that attracting customers from outside the neighborhood is also significant for dispelling stereotypes about the community and promoting a positive representation and political voice for it.

However, not everyone targets an external audience. For example, Rafael, similar to Omar from Santa Ana, positions his business primarily for the local community, even if it means

reducing his customer base. He is aware of the issues associated with attracting outside consumers and tries to mitigate this by closely monitoring that he is reaching the local community by remaining accessible, affordable, and staying true to his values:

I think we're all gentrifiers, when we're opening up businesses in the local community, because our work is trying to bring in people, and it does bring in outside people. but I think it's a matter of what their purpose is...there's people that moved in into this community, and now they're trying to say they're part of it, they put on a facade and they say, oh, I'm here for the community, but once prices start going up or once they see that they can make money from the outside community, then that's when they start calling the new, they start doing all these other things to bring in outsiders, instead of looking what's around them and trying to like do projects here with the community here, and you see that, whether it's from art, whether it's from events, just bringing in, inviting tour groups, that's where you see people's true colors. And it's hard because I can't say the confidence at all that everybody here is to help the community....when it comes times to making the hard decisions where you're really looking at an issue and being on the right side and it may not be popular with everyone, that's when people's true colors show, and that's where you see what someone's really about.

In several stores, the “loyalty” to the local community is also reflected in signs, photographs, trinkets, and clothing adorned with political messages like “Fight gentrification,” “*El Barrio No Se Vende*” (the neighborhood is not for sale), and “*Aztlán* gatekeeper.” These messages seek to resist the entry of gentrifiers into the space and preserve it for the local community. Whether catering to internal or external audiences, commercial *gentefiers* harness the power of their platforms to raise awareness, stimulate dialogue, and advocate for significant political issues within the Latinx community. By establishing workplaces that celebrate Latinx culture, promoting political messages, and actively participating in community activism, these businesses aspire to serve as vehicles for social change and empowerment. They aim to redefine traditional business ownership in the *barrio* by illustrating that business can be a potent instrument for political and social transformation through occupational activism in their day-to-day. **DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION**

This study contributes to the growing literature on occupational activism, or the actions taken by workers within their workplace to address social and political issues, highlighting workers as agents of change in their workplace and beyond (Berg & Kalleberg, 2001; Coley & Schachle, 2023; Cornfield, 2015, 2016, 2023; Cornfield et al., 2019; Hodson, 2001; Pedulla, 2020; Vallas, 2006). Our case studies of business owners in two communities participating in Latinx-led gentrification, or *gentefication* (Ahrens, 2015; Delgado & Swanson, 2019; Huante, 2021; Shmaryahu-Yeshurun, 2024), as a form of occupational activism add perspective to this literature by showing how workers address injustices faced by the communities where they live and work. We show how business owners, as workers with more autonomy (Cornfield, 2015; Cornfield et al., 2019), can employ activism despite having no prior experience in organized social movements but, rather, in response to threats of gentrification in the communities where they own businesses. By focusing on commercial *gentefiers*, our analysis also enriches the field of urban sociology, highlighting the multifaceted altruistic contributions of communities of color's mobility.

These findings demonstrate that business ownership in Barrio Logan and Santa Ana serves as occupational activism and is an alternative to traditional forms of protest against gentrification, such as boycotting new businesses, in favor of culturally sensitive economic development for and by the community. Commercial *gentefiers*, a term we use to refer to business owners who engage in Latinx-led commercial gentrification as a form of occupational activism, occupy a middle ground: they are neither purely economically driven nor entirely oppositional to redevelopment and gentrification; they engage in dilemma work as a result (Chong, 2021). Instead, business owners leverage urban development as a form of political engagement and community contribution. These commercial *gentefiers* are uniquely attuned to issues of identity erasure, racism, and displacement. They frame their businesses as more than economic ventures,

positioning them as political and cultural tools to foster community pride, preserve heritage, and advocate for social justice. Commercial *gentefiers* in this context participate in commercial gentrification as an alternative to displacement, framing their work as economically and politically beneficial. Commercial *gentefiers* view business ownership and their physical presence in the neighborhood as a means of resisting external forces of redevelopment while giving back to their communities. Through active participation, representation, the sale of political products, and the promotion of art and murals, these *gentefiers* amplify their community's political voice and challenge dominant gentrification narratives. As demonstrated in this study, an analysis of similar practices across various Latinx neighborhoods underscores that these are not isolated or singular instances. Instead, they reflect broader patterns worthy of further exploration in other communities facing similar dynamics.

This research also contributes to a deeper understanding of the complexities, challenges, and dilemmas associated with workplace activism among small business owners in the broader context of gentrification. Through their workplace roles, business owners navigate the dual demands of economic survival and political engagement, highlighting their strategies to balance these often-competing priorities. Unlike traditional activism, business owners' actions occur in their workplaces, exposing them to immediate financial risks and forcing them to balance competing priorities: advancing economic interests while maintaining a political voice supporting marginalized populations, leveraging local culture and space versus fostering solidarity with their communities.

One of the key challenges business owners face is utilizing culture to empower and express cultural and political identity rather than merely as a commercialized tool for profit. In our study, galleries, exhibitions, art events, murals, and graffiti significantly promote Latinx empowerment

and amplify local voices through business spaces, countering the cultural erasure often associated with traditional gentrification. However, this approach attracts criticism from activists who argue that commercial *gentefiers* exploit local culture for economic gain. Another challenge for business owners is balancing catering to wealthier clients and maintaining affordable prices for the local community. Amid rising rents and redevelopment projects, these *gentefiers* face competing pressures: serving the working-class community with accessible goods and services versus attracting external consumers—tourists and affluent customers—through higher-priced offerings often out of reach for residents.

In gentrifying neighborhoods, business owners contend with economic survival amidst rising costs, justify their presence, and avoid backlash from activists and residents who may boycott their establishments. As a result, they are further tasked with distinguishing themselves from white gentrifiers. Despite these workplace tensions, or perhaps because of them, business owners adopt strategies to navigate conflicting interests while amplifying their political voice, refusing to forgo their activism.

As such, business owners emerge as vital actors in discussions of occupational activism, especially in marginalized neighborhoods undergoing gentrification. Importantly, these *gentefiers* also represent a source of potential and hope for bolstering the organizing power of marginalized communities. With their economic resources, informational networks, proximity to local organizations, and solidarity with the community, business owners are uniquely positioned to support initiatives that preserve cultural heritage and combat the physical, political, and cultural displacement accompanying gentrification.

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Table 1. Santa Ana and Barrio Logan Neighborhoods Characteristics

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Neighborhood</i>	
	<i>Santa Ana</i>	<i>Barrio Logan</i>
Total population	308,189	4,234
Median household income	\$80,265	\$45,281
Mean age	32.6	31.4
Race and Ethnicity		
% Latino/Hispanic	78.2	60
% White	9.2	26
% Asian	10.6	2.8
% Black	1.2	9.1
% Other	0.8	2.1
% Foreign-born	41.7	21.6
% College graduate	18.5	30.7
% Unemployed	3.4	15.8
% Of households below poverty	12.3	28.3
Household	76,624	1,235

Source: U.S. Census Bureau, 2016-2020 American Community Survey five-year estimates.

Table 2. Participants' Demographics

<i>Variable</i>		<i>Neighborhood</i>	
		<i>Santa Ana</i>	<i>Barrio Logan</i>
Gender	% Male	58	57
	% Female	42	43
Average age		49	38
Place of birth	% Born in neighborhood	0*	15
	% Born in the city	42	45
	% Born in the USA	91	2
	% Born in Mexico	9	2
	% Married	58	58
Income	% Middle-class	98	95
	% College graduate	49	42
Property Status	% Owner Occupied	28	7
	% Renter Occupied	72	93
Average Business Tenure		12 years	5 years
<i>N</i>		<i>43</i>	<i>40</i>

*Santa Ana does not have comparable residential geographies to Barrio Logan